

We are glad to welcome you to SCENARIOS' second newsletter!

SCENARIOS is a 4-year H2020 Research and Innovation project (RIA) involving 19 partners from 10 European countries and Israel. The goal is to close the knowledge gap and achieve breakthrough TRL advances in the toxicology, detection and remediation of probably the most objectionable and widespread class of contaminants -PFAS-, with an unprecedented energetic balance and virtually no external chemical additives. A major effort is underway to develop Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) of PFAS, including the new generation of congeners, to assist EC and EU countries in decision-making on these substances for environmental safety and human health.

SCENARIOS looks back at its achievements in the second year

From January 23rd to 26th, the team convened in Athens, Greece, for the annual meeting of the H2020-SCENARIOS project, discussing the results from its second year of activity. The meeting commenced at the Technical University of Athens campus, featuring parallel work-package sessions followed by an afternoon LCA & Exploitation workshop and endured for four days of exiting discussions.

It was a pleasure to reunite with Principal Investigators and scientists from each of the 19 research groups, alongside numerous young PhD students and postdocs immersed in investigating per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). Together, we reviewed the accomplishments of the past 12 months.

Remarkable progress was achieved within Pillar 1, focusing on PFAS detection and measurement through smart-sensor-based technologies. Successful proof of concept was attained for electrochemical and Surface Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS) detection systems for PFAS. Teams are now refining specificity and detection limits in preparation for final demonstration activities over the next two years.

Pillar 2, concerning PFAS toxicity, witnessed significant advancements. Five human-related cellular model systems, including three 3D models (lung, intestine, and skin), were established, offering omics data on 34 PFAS congeners. A QSAR model predicting PFAS toxicity and transactivation of the PPAR- α receptor for next-generation congeners is forthcoming, set to become a micro-web service on the Scenarios website.

Ecotoxicology studies explored PFAS effects on invertebrate species, revealing substantial impacts on inflammation, immunity, and behavior, prompting further investigation into neurotoxicity.

Pillar 3 addressed PFAS monitoring and remediation. Biomonitoring of potentially impacted cohorts in Alessandria, Italy, near a next-generation PFAS manufacturing plant, has commenced. Concurrently, a full Surface Active Foam Fractionation (SAFF) unit installed in Korsör, Denmark, is concentrating PFAS from groundwater, with a focus on removing short-chain congeners and destroying PFAS concentrate using cold plasma.

Substantial progress has also been made in policy-making, exploitation, dissemination, and communication of SCENARIOS results. Participation in policy events, Horizon Booster Results programs, and numerous conferences across Europe and beyond has facilitated knowledge sharing. Workshops with international PFAS experts and session organization at prestigious conferences such as SETAC23 in Dublin, underscore our commitment to advancing PFAS research and aligning with the goals of the European Green Deal.

Together with PROMISCES and ZEROPM we created a video presentation with the help and support of the Horizon Results Booster that can be seen in [SCENARIOS YouTube channel](#).

There is also a video from our colleagues from FORTH with the title "Presentation of a Computational Fluid Dynamic approach on Korsör site in Denmark".

NEWS

SCENARIOS second GA in Athens

Last week we held the second general assembly in Athens where all work packages have given an update on the work done so far. Results from two years of work which includes valuable results and experiences. During the first day all partners contributing with technology and data to LCA participated in the exploitation workshop, while in the morning parallel sessions took place for different work packages to meet and discuss future steps.

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Safeguarding Groundwater

The World Bank refers to Groundwater as "the hidden wealth of nations" in its report on the economics of groundwater in times of climate change (2023). Groundwater is a vital resource for drinking water, irrigation, and industrial use. However, it is also vulnerable to pollution from a variety of sources, including agriculture, industry, and urban development.

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Intense need for PFAS innovative methods for degradation and detection of PFAS

Comprising more than 4 700 chemicals, perfluorinated and polyfluorinated alkyl substances (PFAS) are a group of widely used, man-made chemicals that accumulate over time in humans and in the environment. PFAS are used in non-stick pans, paper products, textiles, firefighting foam, electronics and other products.

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SCENARIOS research on PFAS toxicity

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are man-made chemicals that are being used in almost all industry branches and that are also prominent in our daily lives. This group of chemicals comprises more than 10,000 substances. Because of their water-, fat-, and dirt-repellent properties they are used in surface coatings and can be found in numerous consumer products such as food packages, non-stick cookware,

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First periodic report meeting in Patras

SCENARIOS consortium gathered during the last week of July for the First Review meeting with EU officials. The meeting went well and we prepared the path for the coming months, correcting the little needs to be corrected and advancing on the previously planned research and implementation tasks.

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The SCENARIOS business cases – An exploitation-oriented culture, based on environmental remediation and looking at the technology, market, and standards development.

The SCENARIOS project will provide pilot solutions for the detection, (bio)monitoring, long-term toxicity and risk assessment, pollution control, and remediation of Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). These SCENARIOS technological developments need to be prepared in order to accelerate their market adoption and generate maximum awareness among the interested stakeholders.

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Perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in food webs: a global review and future research agenda

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are a group of man-made chemicals that are known for their unique chemical properties and persistent nature. The major sources of PFAS have been identified in municipal waste disposal sites, landfills, wastewater treatment facilities, and biosolids. Nowadays, these substances can be found both in industrialized regions and remote areas.

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The importance of measuring PFAS in the environment

Robust detection of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) congeners in different matrices and samples is a must. Scenarios scientists report on the current state of the art in measuring PFASs in environmental matrices and complex samples.

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PUBLICATIONS & RESULTS

On top of the six scientific papers related to the project published in the previous year, we have increased its number to eight, plus four illustrations on the vermichar approach:

- **Degradation of organic pollutants combining plasma discharges generated within soil with TiO₂ and ZnO catalysts: Comparative analysis, optimization and mechanisms** [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- **A Systematic Review of Deep Learning Methodologies Used in the Drug Discovery Process with Emphasis on In Vivo Validation** [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- **Vermichar production in SCENARIOS** [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- **Vermicomposting** [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- **Vermichar for the treatment of PFAS-contaminated soils** [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- **Graphical abstract for article in "The Handbook of Environmental Chemistry: Soil Remediation Science and Technology."** [▶ LEARN MORE](#)

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